

Traditional Remedies to Commercial Products: Formulation of Herbal Mosquito Repellent Candles with Growing Natural Product Marketing India

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ABSTRACT

Modern and conventional herbal therapy for illness prevention primarily derives from herbal plants, which contain a variety of biologically active substances that are beneficial for enhancing one's quality of life. As an environmentally responsible substitute for chemical repellents. Combining a suitable wax base for maximum burning, the candle contains a blend of natural essential oils, such as lemon, lavender, and rosemary, which are known for their ability to repel insects. The number of illnesses brought on by mosquitoes is increasing day by day. Yellow fever, dengue, zika virus, filariasis, malaria, and chicken-gunya are among the illnesses that are frequently brought on by mosquitoes. The created candle was tested at room temperature in the lab. The created candle is assessed for Organoleptic Character color, Fragrance, texture, testing for irritability, flammable Test. human's health and insects can benefit from the use of herbal mosquito repellent candles. To ensure safety for indoor usage while optimizing efficacy, the formulation process required figuring out the perfect concentrations for each essential oil. Through field testing in controlled circumstances, the duration and efficacy of mosquito deterrent were measured in order to assess the candles' repellent ability. The assessment also included physical attributes including stability, scent throw, and burn time. The outcomes demonstrated that the polyherbal composition considerably decreased mosquito attraction; an ideal mix demonstrated improved efficacy.

Keywords: Type of Mosquito Species, Repellent candle, Life cycle of Mosquito, Herb selection

INTRODUCTION

Mosquito-borne diseases such as malaria, dengue fever, and several kinds of encephalitis are major public health concerns as they induce significant morbidity and mortality across the world (Tolle 2009). Malaria, transmitted by the Anopheles mosquito, keeps causing a significant illness burden on infants and young children in endemic areas. Malaria caused the deaths of around one million individuals worldwide, with an estimated 243 million cases. The Aedes aegypti mosquito, which transmits dengue fever, is responsible for 50-100 million infections each year, resulting in thousands of deaths (WHO 2009). Encephalitis is transmitted mainly by the Culex species mosquito. There are 30,000–50,000 reported. Japanese encephalitis cases and 10,000–15,000 deaths from encephalitis annually (Gould & Solomon 2008). Mosquito control and personal protection from mosquito bites are currently accepted as key measures used to control mosquito bites. Using

repellents is one of the most effective methods to protect oneself from mosquito-borne diseases. N, N-diethyl-m-toluamide (DEET) is widely useful as a mosquito repellent (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2008; Environmental Protection Agency 2007). The use of plant-derived agents such as citronella is an alternative repellent, which has been registered as an insect repellent from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (Environmental Protection Agency 2008). Mosquitoes are attracted towards man because of the presence of lactic acid and Carbon (IV) Oxide in human sweat. The attraction is caused by Chemoreceptors present in the antennae of mosquito's which perceive the smell of the sweat. The special role of natural mosquito repellent is to mask human scent. Most plants contain compounds that can be used to prevent attack from plant eating insects. These can be categorized as repellents, feeding deterrents, toxins

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and growth regulators. Repellents from plant origin is not hazardous to human and domestic animals, they are easily biodegradable. Natural products are safe for human when compared to that of synthetic compounds (Patel and Oswald 2012). Hence, there is need to launch extensive search to explore eco-friendly biological materials for control of insect pests. To produce a safe and non-toxic composition, we try to incorporate natural herbal substances and essential oils with proven mosquito-repelling characteristics, such as Beeswax, Camphor, Tulsi, Neem, Orange, Lemongrass, Marigold, Rosemary oil, Lavender Oil, Lemon Oil.

The following list includes the various mosquito species and the illnesses they can spread:

- **Aedes mosquito:**

Zika virus, yellow fever, dengue fever, and West Nile fever are among the illnesses spread by the Aedes mosquito. The primary way to identify them is by looking for black and white marks on their bodies and legs.

- **Aedes albopictus:**

Aedes albopictus also called Asian tiger. In addition to some filarial worms like *Dirofilaria immitis*, it is the cause of other viral infections like Dengue fever, Zika fever, and yellow fever virus. Southeast Asian regions that are tropical or subtropical are home to them.

- **Anopheles mosquito:**

Anopheles mosquitoes are known to cause malaria, brain tremors, and *dirofilaria immitis*. They are typically found in tropical and colder climates, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa.

- **Yellow Fever mosquito:**

The yellow fever mosquito spreads diseases such as dengue fever, Zika fever, yellow fever, and many more. This mosquito was initially found in African countries but is currently found throughout the world's tropical and subtropical regions. Written 5000 years ago in India, the Rig-Veda is the oldest literature in Hindu civilization. The Atharvana Veda makes far more extensive and altered use of plant material. An Upaveda named Ayurveda was a part of Atharvana Veda. Ayurveda treatises such as Sushruta and Charaka Samhita are well-known. The Charaka Samhita lists 64 minerals, 57 medications derived from animals, and 395 medicinal plants as therapeutic agents. The main insecticides used in the Americas, according to the WHO pesticide review, are pyrethroids and organophosphates. Examples of chemical-based insect repellents used on mosquitoes include DEET. Although this insecticide is registered, there are potential adverse effects and cautions, such as irritation of the skin and eyes and insomnia. Synthetic pyrethroids such as sumithrin, resmethrin, and permethrin are used to kill adult mosquitoes. In insect repellents, a variety of plant extracts are also utilized. Researchers are discovering that several plant-based insect repellents, such as eucalyptus and neem powders, are just as effective as DEET. Butylated hydroxyl toluene (B.H.T.), an antioxidant comprised in various repellents, can damage the liver or kidneys if ingested or inhaled. Due to their insecticidal or repellent properties, plant-based repellents are becoming more and more used as a mosquito control strategy. Plant powders can be found naturally and have a potent smell. Fine particles and a green colour are typical characteristics of plant powder.

Life Cycle of Mosquito

Figure 1: Life Cycle of Mosquito

Mosquito repellent

To keep mosquitoes from flying into or staying on areas, especially human skin, is the aim of insect repellents. These are substances that are used on skin, clothing, and other surfaces. They work by making the treated area repellent or uninviting to mosquitoes, so reducing the likelihood of mosquito bites and the transmission of diseases including dengue fever, malaria, and the Zika virus. There are several ways to repel mosquitoes: sprays, lotions, creams, coils, and electrical gadgets.

Type of mosquito repellent

- **Chemical repellents**

Include picaridin, ethyl butyl acetyl amino propionate, and DEET.

- **Natural repellent**

Citronella, lavender, rosemary, and neem oils, as well as lime Eucalyptus oil.

- **Wearable repellent**

Repellent bracelets and clip-on devices are examples of wearable repellents.

- **Globally repulsive**

Candles, coils, dhoops, plug-ins, electric diffusers, and sticks are examples of globally repulsive.

- **Mosquito Repellent clothing**

Clothes coated with permethrin is considered mosquito repellent.

Herbs Selection

A kind of candle used to repel insects using natural components is called a polyherbal mosquito repellent candle. Typically, natural herbs derived from plants are used, together with their essential oils, which have the ability to repel mosquitoes. Mosquito control treatments with a chemical base are frequently utilized, however because of their synthetic ingredients, they are harmful to humans. There is a rising need in the market for the creation of herbal-based insect repellents as a result of these toxicity issues

Advantage of Natural Insect Repellent Candle

- Natural Insect Repellent Candles are portable, lightweight, and simple to use.
- They are eco- friendly as well as biodegradable.
- In which contain the essential oil show the repellent activity.
- They are non-irritating, non-poisonous, simple to produce, and have insect-repelling properties

Table 1: Natural Herbs

Sr. No	Herb Name	Synonym	Biological Source /Family	Chemical Constituents	Uses	Image
1.	Bees Wax	Yellow wax, Cera alba	Honeycomb of the honey bee, Apis mellifera Linn and other species of Apis/Apidae.	Ester of fatty acids and long –chain alcohols.	Candles, Cosmetics, Lubricants, Waterproofing Agent	
2.	Camphor	Gum Camphor	volatile oil of Cinnamomum camphora (L.) /Lauraceae	cineole, pinene, camphene	Antipruritic and Anti-infective	
3.	Tulsi	Sacred basil, Holy basil.	fresh and dried leaves of Ocimum sanctum Linn. / Labiatae	Eugenol, Eugenol-methyl-ether, Carvacrol	Antibacterial and Insecticidal, Stimulant, Aromatic, Spasmolytic, and Diaphoretic	
4.	Neem	Nimba, Arista	Fresh and dried leaves of Azadirachta indica/ Meliaceae	Azadirachtin, Nimbin, Nimbidin, Nimbidol, Gednin, Sodium Nimbin ate.	As an insecticide or mosquito repellent in herbal mosquito repellent candles. antibacterial and antifungal qualities	
5.	Orange	Cortex Limonis	Lemon peel is outer part of pericarp of tye ripe fruit of citrus Limonis Burm/Rutaceae.	sugar, cellulose, pectins, hemicellulose, Vitamin C, Flavonoid.	prevent chronic diseases such as cancer and heart diseases essential oils with mosquito-repelling properties, like limonene	
6.	Lemon Grass	Fever grass, Cochin grass, Malabar grass, soft heads, oily heads.	It obtained from fresh Aerial part of Cymbopogon citratus/Poaceae.	Citral Isoneral, Citonellal, Citronellol, Geraniol, Isogeraniol,	citronella oil actually prevents mosquitoes	
7.	Marigold	Calendula, geranium, anemone.	Its genus of about 50 species of annual herbs of Calendula Officinalis. / Daisy.	Limonene, Terpinolene, (Z)- myroxide, Piperitone, Piperitenone, Piperitenone oxide and b - caryophyllene	marigold flower petals has 100% mortality rate of mosquito larvae and acts as a repellent	
8.	Rosemary Oil	Romero, popular plant, Hoja de romeo.	It consists fresh and dry flower of rosmarinus officinalis. / Lamiaceae.	cineole, Camphor, Camphene	depression, emotional disturbance, intercostal neuralgia, headaches, migraines, and sleeplessness	

9.	Levender Oil	Levenda, Foreign oil, Espliego	It consists of fresh Flowering tops Levendula Officinalis, L. augustifolia	Volatile Oil contain linalyl acetate, linolool, cineol, terpin-4-ol	Antioxidant-property chemicals including linalyl acetate and linalool are found in lavender oil, to relieve fatigue, headaches, and nervous illnesses	
10.	Lemon Oil	Citrus, Citrus Fruit, Cortex limonis, lemon peel	It consists of fresh peel of ripe fruit Citrus Limonis/Rutaceae	Lemon oil contains terpenes, Sesquiterpenes, aldehydesester s.	Chemicals found in lemon eucalyptus destroy fungus and deter insects. Mosquito repellent made with lemon eucalyptus oil is used by people	

Uses

Chemicals found in lemon eucalyptus destroy fungus and deter insects. Mosquito repellent made with lemon eucalyptus oil is used by people.

Formulation of Poly Herbal Mosquito Repellent Candle:

Table 2: Formulation table

Sr No.	Ingredient Name	Quantity	Uses
1.	Beeswax	50gm	Insect repellent
2.	Camphor	2gm	Burning, Room Freshener.
3.	Tulsi	2gm	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant
4.	Neem	4gm	Insecticide
5.	Orange	2gm	Fragrance
6.	Lemon grass	4ml	Insect repellent
7.	Marigold	4ml	Insect repellent
8.	Rosemary Oil	8-10 drop	Flavouring agent
9.	Levender Oil	8-10 drop	Insect repellent
10.	Lemon Oil	5-7 drop	Aroma

Procedure

- Weigh a piece of beeswax accurately.
- Make tiny slices in the beeswax and use a heating mantle to melt it in a beaker.
- In a beaker, mix the camphor, orange peel powder, and Tulsi powder after the components have melted sufficient, stirring continuously.
- In the beaker, mix the juice of the marigold and lemongrass.
- After that, add the oils of lemon, lavender, and rosemary. Whisk for a full fifteen minutes after adding each component.
- Pour the mixture into the size mould above.

- Allowed to cool at room temperature.
- After three to five hours, take the candle out of the mould.

Evaluation of the insect-repelling candle formulated from multiple plants

• Organoleptic Character

To evaluate the aroma, shade, and texture of the formulation, visual inspection of the mixture was used in this test.

• Color

Green

- **Fragrance**

The odor of the formulation was discovered to be pleasant.

- **Texture**

A homogeneous formulation was discovered.

- **Testing for irritability**

- It was found that lighting a prepared insect repellent candle caused no skin discomfort.

- **Flammable Test**

The created candle was evaluated for flammability to find out more about the behaviors that repel insects. It also burned well in terms of burning time. Finally, a flammability test was performed to confirm the candle's apparent flammability in the lab using the spotting technique

CONCLUSION

Neem extract has an active component called azadirachtin, which may have the potential to function as a natural insecticide. Azadirachtin has been shown to directly harm a mosquito's reproductive cycle, feeding habits, and body development in addition to functioning as a poison when consumed by the insect. If you want to avoid mosquito-borne diseases like dengue and malaria, candle serve as a practical, economical, and effective method. As it is constructed of natural substances this mosquito repellent candle won't cause skin irritation or allergic reactions. Because the herbal mosquito repellent candle is lightweight, it is really simple to use and carry. Both human health and mosquitoes can be protected by using an herbal mosquito repellent candle. The use of essential oils and plants as a mosquito repellent was shown to be very effective and safe. Smoke from the market's mosquito coils might cause respiratory problems, especially for people who have asthma, COPD, or other respiratory disorders. A mosquito repellent with a natural foundation was successfully created during this research study. The Candle proven as extremely reliable as well as secure. This organic repellent's formulation produces the greatest level of

repellent against mosquitoes and is cheap, secure, non-toxic, and easy to use.

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